

Synthesis and electronic properties of anthracenyl 5,10-dihydrophenazine derivatives

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ABSTRACT: A series of seven novel anthracenyl 5,10-dihydrophenazine derivatives was synthesized by Boc protection-assisted approach. The prepared compounds were structurally characterized by ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR, mass spectrometry and single crystal structure analysis. The electronic properties of the new compounds were examined by UV-vis absorption, photoluminescence spectroscopy and cyclic voltammetry. Structural analysis revealed a nearly planar dihydrophenazine core with strongly twisted peripheral aryl groups. The parent π -extended derivatives exhibited broad red to near-infrared emission arising from low-energy excited states, whereas peripheral functionalization significantly modified their photophysical behavior. Measurements of the emission in solvents with different polarities revealed pronounced solvatochromism. The analysis of the UV-vis spectra of the compounds in chlorinated solvents and upon addition of ethyl iodide revealed enhanced singlet-triplet absorption attributed to a heavy-atom effect. Electrochemical measurements showed in all compounds two reversible oxidations whose potentials could be systematically tuned by electron-donating and electron-withdrawing substituents. These results demonstrate that Boc-assisted synthetic approach provides efficient access to previously inaccessible π -extended dihydrophenazines and that π -extension together with peripheral functionalization offers an effective strategy for tailoring their optical and redox properties for potential application in photocatalysis and organic optoelectronics.

■ INTRODUCTION

N,N-Diaryldihydrophenazines are polycyclic heteroaromatic compounds containing an antiaromatic ring with two nitrogen atoms.¹ They have attracted considerable interest for applications in organic ferromagnets,² hole-transport materials,³ organic light-emitting diodes,⁴ photocatalyst^{5, 6} and organocatalyzed atom-transfer radical polymerization (O-ATRP).^{7, 8} Extended conjugation in these systems is particularly important for the design of organic electronic materials. Recent studies have shown that *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazines possessing an eight-electron antiaromatic core stabilized by an extended aromatic framework can strongly influence electronic properties, including molecular conductivity.¹ In addition, *N,N*-Diaryldihydrophenazines have also emerged as attractive redox-active and photoactive scaffolds, particularly because π -extended derivatives can serve as organic photocatalysts and potential alternatives to precious-metal complexes such as iridium- and ruthenium-based catalysts.⁵

To date, the only highly hindered, symmetrical example is a 1-naphthalene-extended *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazine.⁷ The high reactivity of dihydrophenazines makes their synthesis challenging and limits coupling with sterically demanding partners such as anthracene, leaving these structures largely unexplored. To address this challenge, various catalysts have been examined to activate such hindered couplings with a mixed success. We hypothesized that the limited effectivity of the coupling is not only the result of steric hindrance but also of the intrinsic instability of the dihydrophenazine core, which can undergo back-aromatization to phenazine.

To investigate this hypothesis, we developed *tert*-butoxycarbonyl (*t*-Boc)-assisted strategy aimed at suppressing the back-

aromatization of dihydrophenazine during derivatization. Herein we show that this strategy is effective in overcoming the high reactivity of dihydrophenazine and enables preparation of both symmetrical and mon-symmetrical *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazines. To demonstrate the generality of the approach, we synthesized a series of dihydrophenazines functionalized with naphthalene, anthracene and several functionalized anthracenes (Figure 1). The electronic properties of the newly

Figure 1. Molecular structure of the newly synthesized π -extended *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazine and its functional-group-substituted derivatives. 5-(anthracen-9-yl)-10-(naphthalen-1-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**1**), 5-(anthracen-9-yl)-10-(naphthalen-2-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**2**), 5,10-di(anthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**3**), 5,10-bis(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**4**), 5,10-bis(10-methoxyanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**5**), dimethyl 10,10'-(phenazine-5,10-diyl)bis(anthracene-9-carboxylate) (**6**), 5-(10-methoxyanthracen-9-yl)-10-(10-nitroanthracen-9-yl)-5,10-dihydrophenazine (**7**).

Scheme 1 Synthetic route to π -extended *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazine derivatives through Boc protection.

prepared compounds were characterized by cyclic voltammetry, UV-visible absorption and emission spectroscopies. TD-DFT calculations were used to help interpret the experimental observations. The prepared compounds may find use in optoelectronic applications and may also serve as photoactivated organocatalysts for efficient polymerizations.⁸ In addition, they represent promising precursors for nitrogen-doped nanographenes.⁹

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Syntheses

In our effort to synthesize the *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazines we initially examined the direct Buchwald-Hartwig C-N coupling of dihydrophenazine with anthracene-based coupling partners. However, instead of obtaining the desired *N,N*-diarylated products, the reaction was accompanied by oxidative back-aromatization of the dihydrophenazine core to phenazine. The isolation of phenazine from the coupling reaction confirmed that aromatization competes strongly with C-N bond formation. This observation suggested that the key limitation is not only steric hindrance from the bulky aryl partner, but also the intrinsic instability of the reduced dihydrophenazine framework under the coupling conditions.

Using this insight, we then tested a new strategy (**Scheme 1**) based on *tert*-butoxycarbonyl (Boc) protection of dihydrophenazine core, aimed suppressing its back-aromatization and enable stepwise arylation. Mono-protection of dihydrophenazine with a Boc group stabilized one nitrogen center and allowed subsequent C-N coupling with anthracene and substituted anthracene derivatives, affording the corresponding Boc-protected intermediates in low to high yields. The coupling efficiency was strongly affected by the amount of the base employed, likely because diarylamine-type nitrogen centers are relatively difficult to deprotonate during the catalytic cycle.¹⁰ We found that the use of excess of a strong base NaO^tBu was required to promote the reaction efficiently and improve the yield. Subsequent deprotection, followed by coupling at the second nitrogen atom, afforded the target *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazines in moderate to low yields (23-60%). The lower yields in the final step are likely associated with impurities generated during deprotection, as well as the renewed sensitivity of the free dihydrophenazine intermediate toward oxidative back-aromatization.

Using this approach, we synthesized a series of novel π -extended *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazines (**1**) to (**7**) shown in Fig.

1. This series of compounds was selected to test the generality of the synthetic approach and to evaluate how π -extension and aryl substituent effects influence the electronic, photophysical and redox properties of the dihydrophenazine scaffold.

Structural characterization

The structures of all the compounds were structurally characterized by ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR, mass spectrometry (see Supporting Information (SI)). In addition, structural characterization by X-ray diffraction analysis of single crystals was performed for two of the prepared compounds (**1**) and (**2**). The single crystals were produced by slow diffusion from dichloromethane/hexane solutions. The results of the structural analysis are summarized in Fig. 2.

In (**1**), the C-N-C bond angles involving the aryl substituents and the central core are 119.5° and 118.8°, while the C-N-C angles within the central core are approximately 120.5°. These values are close to 120°, indicating an approximately trigonal planar geometry around the nitrogen centers. The C-N-C-C torsion angles around the phenazine core are 176.9° and -176.1°, suggesting that the core adopts a nearly planar geometry. In contrast, the torsion angles between the phenazine core and the aryl substituents are -90.5° and -96.4°, indicating that the aryl substituents are strongly twisted relative to the core structure. The molecular packing shows short intermolecular C⋯H

Figure 2 Structures of (**1**) and (**2**), determined by single-crystal X-ray diffraction. Top: top views, bottom: side views.

contacts with distances of 2.71-2.74 Å, suggesting weak C-H... π -type interactions between neighboring molecules.

A similar structural arrangement is observed for **(2)**. The C-N-C bond angles involving the aryl substituents and the central core are 119.6° and 118.8°, respectively, while the C-N-C angles within the central core are 121.0° and 120.3°. These values also indicate a trigonal-planar geometry around the nitrogen centers. The torsion angles around the phenazine core are 171.7° and 168.2°, showing that the core remains nearly planar. In contrast, the torsion angles between the aryl substituents and the core are -87.1° and 90.6°, confirming that the aryl groups are strongly twisted relative to the core. The molecular packing of **(2)** also exhibits short intermolecular C...H contacts with distances of 2.55-2.76 Å, suggesting weak C-H... π -type interactions between neighboring molecules.

■ Characterization of electronic structure

Electronic absorption and photoluminescence. The UV-VIS absorption and photoluminescence spectra of the newly synthesized *N,N*-diaryl dihydrophenazine are summarized in Fig.

3. The absorption and photoluminescence maxima for all the compounds are listed in Table 1. The absorption spectra of the compounds in the 300-400 nm range exhibit characteristic vibronically structured peaks commonly attributed to the $\pi - \pi^*$ electronic excitations localized within the phenothiazine core.¹¹ The parental π -extended derivatives **(1)**, **(2)**, **(3)**, without functional group substitution, exhibit similar absorption profiles, with maximum absorption observed at 368 nm. Although the absorption spectra of the substituted derivatives **(4)**, **(5)** and **(6)** have similar overall shapes to those of the parent compounds, the absorption maxima shift the longer wavelengths at 373, 372, 381, respectively and their absorption tails are slightly shifted toward the visible region. The push-pull derivative **(7)** shows a more distinct absorption behavior, with a maximum of absorption observed at 381 nm and a broad absorption tail extended into the visible region.

Photoluminescence spectra of all compounds show a distinct emission band in the region 400 - 660 nm with the peak varying from 412 nm for **(1)** to 439 nm for compounds **(5)** and **(6)**. In the compounds **(1)**, **(2)** and **(4)** the emission bands show

Figure 3. UVVIS absorption (blue traces) and photoluminescence (red traces) spectra of: (a) **(1)**, (b) **(2)**, (c) **(3)**, (d) **(4)**, (e) **(5)**, (f) **(6)** and (g) **(7)** in toluene. All spectra are normalized to maximum of absorbance and photoluminescence.

Table 1. Summary of optical electrochemical characterization of the prepared compounds.

Compound	A_{max}^a (nm)	$^1PL_{max}^b$ (nm)	$^3PL_{max}^c$ (nm)	$E^{1/2}_{1,ox}^d$ (V)	$E^{1/2}_{2,ox}^d$ (V)	$E^{1/2}_{3,ox}^d$ (V)
(1)	368	412	709	0.35	1.29	-
(2)	368	412	719	0.30	1.16	-
(3)	368	415	700	0.37	1.37	-
(4)	373	419	-	0.57	1.49	-
(5)	372	439	-	0.17	0.74	-
(6)	381	439	780	0.46	1.43	-
(7)	381	433	-	0.27	0.50	1.49

^aMaximum of the lowest energy absorption band multiplet measured in toluene. ^bPosition of the photoluminescence maximum assigned to the emission from the singlet excited state. Measured in toluene at room temperature. ^cPosition of the photoluminescence maximum assigned to the emission from the triplet excited state. Measured in toluene at room temperature. ^dHalfwave oxidation potentials vs. standard hydrogen electrode (SHE), determined from cyclic voltammograms measured in DCM, 0.1M TBAPF₆ at room temperature, using glassy carbon working electrode and silver nitrate reference electrode.

distinct vibronic features mirroring the shape of the absorption band. We attribute these high energy bands to singlet-singlet transition-based fluorescence.

Interestingly, compounds (1), (2), (3) and (6) show a distinct dual photoluminescence with the second emission peak observed with the maxima at 709, 719, and 700 and 780 nm, respectively. The broad and strongly red-shifted emission suggests the involvement of low-energy excited states with local excitation or charge-transfer character.⁷ Although triplet-related excited-state processes are the most likely source of this emission, further studies, such as lifetime measurements, oxygen-sensitivity experiments, or temperature-dependent emission measurements are needed to confirm the involvement of triplet excited states.

Unlike the parent derivatives and compound (6), the rest of the functional group-substituted compounds did not show broad red-region emission. This suggests that the low-energy emission observed in the parent molecules is likely related to the excited-state behavior of the peripheral anthracene moiety, which is significantly affected by the functional group substitution.

Redox properties. Figure 4 shows the cyclic voltammograms (CVs) of all prepared compounds (1) to (7) recorded at potentials positive relative to Standard Hydrogen Electrode (SHE). All CVs were recorded in dichloromethane with 0.1 M tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆) as an electrolyte. The cyclic voltammograms of derivatives showed two reversible oxidation processes for compounds (1) to (6) and three reversible oxidation processes for compound (7). The standard potentials for each of the oxidations are summarized in Table 1. The observed oxidations are attributed to the formation of corresponding radical cations and dication. Compounds (5) and (7) are the easiest to oxidize, which is attributed to the presence of electron donating group -OMe. In contrast, the most stable with respect to oxidation is compound (4), which we attribute to the presence of two electron withdrawing -NO₂ functional groups. The reduction of any of the compounds was not observed within the solvent window, indicating that they are quite difficult to reduce. We attribute this observation to the electron-rich and anti-aromatic 4n π-electron *N,N'*-dihydrophenazine core.

Special effects. To better understand the effect of the solvent's environment on the excited states of the newly synthesized *N,N'*-diaryl dihydrophenazine derivatives, we performed comparative photoluminescence measurements in three solvents with different polarities: toluene, chloroform, and THF. The results obtained for (2) are summarized in Figure. 5a. The results show that with increasing solvent polarity, the low energy emission of the compounds shift toward the near-infrared region, with emission maxima at 709, 765, and 770 nm in toluene, chloroform, and THF, respectively. We attribute this solvatochromic behavior to the stabilization of the excited states possessing a distinct dipole moment by more polar solvents. Similar effect was observed for related compounds.⁷

In addition to the solvatochromic effect we also observed that when compounds (1), (2), (3) are dissolved in chloroform, their absorption spectra show weak absorption features near 472, 474, and 479 nm, respectively. These features were not observed in toluene or THF. The effect was further amplified upon addition of increasing concentration of ethyl iodide in the concentration range 0 to 0.8 M in toluene (see Fig 5b). We

Figure 4. Cyclic voltammograms (CV) of studied compounds in 0.1 M TBAPF₆/WE: Glassy carbon, RE: 10 mM Ag/AgNO₃ in 0.1M TBAPF₆ (ACN) and CE: Pt wire.

Figure 5 (a) Normalized emission spectra of **(2)** in toluene, THF and CHCl_3 showing solvent-dependent emission behavior. (b) Changes in the UV-vis absorption spectra of **(2)** with increasing concentration of ethyl iodide in toluene. The inset shows the same data in the absorbance range 0 to 0.1.

attribute these observations to the enhancement of the spin-orbital coupling, induced by an external heavy atom effect, which makes the spin-forbidden direct singlet-to-triplet excitation partially allowed.

TD-DFT modeling

To better understand the experimental observations summarized in the previous section, we used density functional theory (DFT) and Time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) to calculate the electronic structure of all the newly synthesized π -extended and functionalized *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazine derivatives. Frontier molecular orbital analysis revealed that the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) is

in all compounds localized predominantly on the electron-rich dihydrophenazine core. In the case of compounds **(1)** and **(2)** also the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) is localized on the dihydrophenazine core. However, the next unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO+1) is mainly distributed over the π -extended aryl substituents. The spatial separation between HOMO and LUMO+1 suggests that any relevant excitations will have a significant charge-transfer character. Since the charge transfer states are often responsible for observation of solvatochromic effects we tentatively attribute the observed solvatochromic effect to the involvement of LUMO+1 orbitals in the low-energy electronic excitations.

Comparison of the calculated orbital energies shows that π -extension of the *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazine framework does not significantly alter the HOMO energy, consistent with the HOMO being primarily localized on the dihydrophenazine donor core. However, interestingly, the nature of LUMO is distinctly different in compounds **(3)** to **(5)**. Specifically, in these compounds the LUMO is localized primarily on the peripheral anthracene functional groups. Also, addition of functional-group substitution has a pronounced effect on the frontier orbital energies. In particular, the electron-withdrawing nitro-substituted derivative exhibits a markedly stabilized LUMO level resulting in a reduced HOMO–LUMO energy gap. These results are consistent with the results of the electrochemical experiments and support the observed changes in the optical properties.

The TD-DFT calculations were used to better understand the origin of the UV-vis absorption spectra and to examine the nature of the initial photoexcitation events. For **(1)**, **(2)** and **(3)** the calculated $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transitions are dominated by HOMO \rightarrow LUMO excitations and exhibit charge-transfer character with very small oscillator strengths of $f = 0.0000$, 0.0003 , and 0.0000 , respectively. In contrast, the HOMO–1 \rightarrow LUMO transitions are predicted to be optically allowed, with oscillator strengths of $f = 0.2200$, 0.2238 , and 0.4373 and calculated absorption maxima at 356.81, 356.83, and 358.37 nm for **(1)**, **(2)** and **(3)**, respectively. These transitions exhibit predominantly aryl-centered locally excited character rather than donor-acceptor charge-transfer character. This suggests that the

Figure 6. Summary of the results of the TD-DFT modeling of the prepared compounds. Frontier molecular orbital distributions and energy-level diagrams of the synthesized π -extended and functionalized *N,N*-diaryldihydrophenazine derivatives: (a) **(1)**, (b) **(2)**, (c) **(3)**, (d) **(4)**, (e) **(5)**.

observed triplet emission is mainly associated with locally excited states.

■ CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the synthetic challenges associated with π -extended *N,N*-diaryl dihydrophenazine derivatives were addressed through the successful synthesis of novel anthracene-coupled dihydrophenazine derivatives. The photophysical properties of the newly synthesized compounds were systematically investigated and further supported by DFT and TD-DFT calculations. Emission spectroscopy revealed that the non-functionalized derivatives exhibit dual photoluminescence with high energy singlet emission complemented with a low-energy emission, tentatively attributed to relaxation via a low energy triplet excited state. Cyclic voltammetry studies showed that the newly synthesized compounds display two redox processes, while substitution with electron-withdrawing groups at the molecular periphery lowers the HOMO energy level. In addition, the non-functionalized derivatives exhibited solvatochromic behavior with increasing solvent polarity, along with an external heavy-atom effect in the presence of ethyl iodide. Overall, these findings demonstrate that π -extension and peripheral functional group substitution provide effective strategies for tuning the optical and electrochemical properties of *N,N*-diaryl dihydrophenazine-based materials.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Detailed experimental procedures, ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR, mass spectra, additional electronic absorption and photoluminescence spectra, CV of prepared compounds. **The Supporting Information is available free of charge at** <https://>

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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